

EXPERIMENTAL - ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF INTERPHASIAL STRESS AND STRAIN FIELDS IN MWCNT POLYMER COMPOSITES

G. C. Papanicolaou*, E.D.Drakopoulos, K.P.Papaefthymiou

Composite Materials Group, Department of Mechanical and Aeronautical Engineering,
University of Patras, Patras 26500, Hellas.

*E-mail: gpapan@mech.upatras.gr

Fax: +30 2610 997 337

Tel.: +30 2610 997 238

SUMMARY

In the present investigation, the effect of polymer matrix-nanofiber interphase on the stress and strain fields developed at the close vicinity of MWCNT was studied. The recently developed *concept of the hybrid interphase* was applied [1]. According to this concept, the interphase thickness depends on the property considered at the time. Experimental findings combined with analytical and numerical results gave a better understanding for the structural and mechanical performance of epoxy resin-carbon nanotubes composites.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, Interphase, Numerical Analysis, Analytical Modeling.

INTRODUCTION

Nanocomposites constitute a very special category of composite materials. Only a small amount of nano-inclusions is adequate to achieve unique mechanical, electrical and other properties. Carbon nanotubes have gain the scientists' interest since the last ten years due to their unique behavior. Carbon nanotubes were firstly reported by the Russians Lukyanovich, V.M. and Radushkevich, L.V in 1952 [2] but no further investigation took place because of the lack of knowledge to massive production. After an extended research by Iijima, S. in 1991 [3] carbon nanotubes became a new attractive material to Nanotechnology. Thorough investigations in polymer matrix composites reinforced with carbon nanotubes are being developed in an effort to explain their unique behavior. It is worth to mention the exceptional mechanical properties of the nanotubes; the axial Young's modulus and the elongation to break of a SWCNT have been computed in the range of 0.9-1.3 TPa and 30-40% respectively [4-11]. The main difficulty is the manufacturing procedure to be followed in order to produce nanocomposites with desired properties. More precisely, one of the problems encountered is the inclusions tendency to agglomerate resulting to a composite with micro-structure instead of a nano-structure. High speed shearing, ultrasonication, ball milling or a combination of these is used to achieve a good dispersion of the CNT's in the matrix defeating agglomeration as well.

A key-factor for the overall performance of micro- and nano-composites is the polymer-reinforcement interphase which is a third phase created during manufacturing in the area immediately surrounding the fibers, having properties and microstructure different from those of the two main constituents of the composite. The interphase formatted during

manufacturing of the composite is the so-called *structural interphase* [12]. This region can be observed optically and must be distinguished from the *hybrid interphase*. More precisely, by the term “*hybrid interphase*” it is meant the interphase material having a volume fraction which represents the percentage of the bulk matrix surrounding the reinforcement in which a specific matrix property is strongly affected by the existence of the reinforcement, while the hybrid interphase thickness represents the maximum radial distance from the inclusion boundary in which this property varies. This shows that the interphase is not simply a geometrical concept but it is mainly a property-dependent concept [1].

In the present study, epoxy-carbon nanotubes (CNT) nanocomposites were manufactured and mechanically characterized. Four different filler-volume fractions were applied and a high speed shearing manufacturing technique was used. Next, using the hybrid interphase concept, a theoretical investigation of their fiber-matrix interphase region was executed in an effort to compute both analytically and numerically its effect on the interfacial stress and strain fields developed in the area close to CNTs.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Three-point bending specimens were manufactured using SIGMA-ALDRICH[®] 31185 D.E.R.™ 332 epoxy resin system (DGEBA, Di-Glycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A), 132098 TETA hardener (Triethylenetetramine) reinforced with Nanothinx S.A. © NTX1 MWNTs. High speed shearing was utilized to disperse the nanotubes in the resin using the high speed dissolver type Dispermat AE, VMA Getzmann GmbH. After several preliminary tests, for achieving better dispersion, the process was finally defined as follows: two hours mixing the resin with nanotubes in vacuum at 2300 rpm and 50°C. Next, the hardener was added while mixing procedure was continuing. Finally, the mixture was put into special moulds having the exact dimensions of three point bending specimens to be used. Curing process consisted of heating the specimens in an oven for 24h at 80°C. Four different fiber loadings (0%, 0.3%, 1%, 2%, and 3% w_f (%) MWNT's) were applied. A displacement rate of 1mm/min was applied in all three-point bending experiments. The final results are shown in the following figures.

Figure 1a shows the exact values for the bending modulus as a function of w_f (%) while Figure 1b shows the relative improvement or degradation of the modulus on the basis of matrix modulus. From these Figures, one can observe that specimens reinforced with 2% w_f showed a degradation in modulus when compared with the matrix modulus while, in contrast, specimens reinforced with 0.3, 1 and 3% w_f with CNTs showed a relative increase in modulus. Significant change of 10.6% and 14.03% was measured for 0.3% w_f and 3% w_f respectively. In addition, as shown in Figures 2 and 3 a general reduction in both flexural strength and failure strain was observed. The higher the CNT weight fraction is, the more brittle the nanocomposite becomes. This type of mechanical behavior can be attributed to more than one reason. Amongst the principal reasons are the adhesion and agglomeration. Besides these two factors, there are many others that should be taken into account in order to see what is behind the above behaviour (fig.2). In a composite with high fiber volume fraction, one may deduce two possible microstructures in addition to that where particles are randomly dispersed. In the first case, the resin is completely entrapped within the filler aggregates or clusters, with fibers touching each other. In the second type of microstructure, the composite contains a mix

of regions of resin entrapped within fiber clusters. In principal, such composites would consist of regions with randomly dispersed fillers, but with each region containing a different volume fraction [17]. Finally, the effect of degree of mixing is something that plays significant role. Mixing time period is directly combined with the dispersion of the nano-fibers. In order to improve the properties of filled polymers, decreasing the aggregate size and the void concentration is needed. Two main methods are used to decrease the size of polymer-filler aggregates. These are (1) increase the local shear stresses of the matrix in order to break down the aggregates and (2) optimize the adhesion characteristics to improve the degree of dispersion of the filler.

THEORETICAL APPROACH OF THE HYBRID INTERPHASE MODEL

Micromechanical modeling needs many assumptions. Some typical assumptions is that fibers are perfectly cylindrical, unidirectional, continuous and uniformly spaced. Typical material assumptions used are: (i) all phases behave in a linearly elastic manner; (ii) the fibers are transversely isotropic; (iii) the global composite behaviour can be modeled by a representative volume element (RVE) (see Fig.4).

Assuming a periodic configuration of fibers, micromechanical analysis requires the selection of a proper RVE, which must contain a single fiber, adjoining interphase and bulk matrix, and must be subject to appropriate constraints. Hybrid interphase is not an assumption and it has been proved experimentally [13-15]. The concept of the hybrid interphase is based on two assumptions. The first one accepts a non-homogeneous interphase whose material properties depend on the respective properties of a homogeneous fiber and matrix, and thickness depending on volumetric composition of composite [16]. The second assumption introduces imperfect adhesion between fiber and matrix materials (eq.2) by proper definition of material properties.

As shown in previous publications, the degradation of the elastic properties within the hybrid interphase region is given by:

$$P_i(r) = P_m + (k_p P_f - P_m) \exp\left(-\frac{k_p}{1-k_p} \frac{P_t}{P_i} \frac{r-r_f}{r_f}\right), \quad r_f \leq r \leq r_{iE}, \quad (1)$$

where

- P_m is the property referring to the matrix (E_m, ν_m)
- P_f is the property referring to the fiber (nanotube) (E_m, ν_m)
- P_i is the respective property within the interphase (E_i, ν_i)
- P_l & P_t are the macroscopic properties for the bulk composite along the longitudinal and the transverse direction respectively
- k_p is the fiber-matrix adhesion efficiency coefficient depending on the property (k_E, k_ν)

These coefficients (k_E, k_ν) describe equivalently the efficiency of bonding for the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio, respectively, defined by the equations

$$k_E = \frac{E_i(r_f^+)}{E_f}, \quad k_\nu = \frac{\nu_i(r_f^+)}{\nu_f} \quad (2)$$

These equations impose jumps on material properties and can take values $0 \leq k_p \leq 1$. The limited value $k_p=1$ describes a compliant interphase with perfect adhesion conditions, in which full stress transfer occurs. When one of these is zero no stress transfer occurs on account of no adhesion. In real conditions of imperfect adhesion, where $0 < k_p < 1$, only a percentage of the stresses are transferred from the fiber to the matrix through the interphase. The coefficients can be calculated by the following equation

$$k_p = \frac{P_c - P_m}{P_f - P_m} \frac{1}{\nu_f}, \quad (3)$$

where P_c is the composite property value as experimentally measured
 ν_f is the fiber volume fraction

Figures 4 and 5 show the modulus and the Poisson's ratio variation within the hybrid interphase area. As it is shown, interphase thickness corresponding to each one of the above properties has a different extent, while the abrupt variation of the property value observed at the fiber-matrix boarder strongly depends on the fiber-matrix degree of adhesion. Additionally, the distribution of the stress-strain field along the interphase is also affected by the fiber-matrix degree of adhesion.

Next, the hybrid interphase model was used for the numerical evaluation of the stress and strain field developed within the interphasial area for the MWCNT nanocomposite. Results showed that most of the bulk matrix is transformed into interphasial material having different properties from those of the virgin polymer matrix (table 1).

The fiber-matrix adhesion efficiency coefficient for the nanocomposites studied in this work was found to be equal to 0.185 (eq.3) for $\nu_f=0.25\%$. Assuming that this coefficient is valid, for the specific fiber volume fraction then the interphase regions of two successive fibers overlap to each other rendering the matrix material a modified material having properties completely different from the bulk. At higher volume fractions, where the distance between two successive fibers is smaller it is obvious that the matrix will be completely transformed, as well.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Geometric complexity and material inhomogeneities of the RVE demand the numerical approximation of stress and load transfer analysis. In the present study, finite element procedures have been utilized to study the response of FRP incorporating a hybrid interphase region. The geometry of the model shown in figure 4 requires axisymmetric analysis associated with appropriate material inhomogeneities.

In the proposed model, it was assumed that a fiber with the properties shown in table 2 can simulate a MWCNT. In addition, it was assumed that the fiber has a constant radius $r_f = 13$ nm and half-length $L_f = 15.38 r_f$, while the fiber volume fraction is a global independent variable. Figure 6 depicts the corresponding finite element model for a volume fraction $\nu_f = 0.25\%$ ($w_f=0.3\%$). The mesh refinement in the regions where high material degradation or high stress concentration is expected (i.e. at the exact fiber-

interphase boarder) to occur is apparent. Table 1 shows the size of the finite element model.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to study the effect of the existence of interphase in MWCNT-epoxy resin nanocomposites, the above-developed hybrid interphase model has been utilized in finite element procedures. According to the model shown in fig.6, for imperfect adhesion condition the stress field in the interphasial area is presented in figs.7-8. Finally, a theoretical model developed in a previous publication [19] in order to compare the values with the finite element model, was applied.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study a series of MWCNT-resin materials with different fiber volume fractions were manufactured and mechanically characterized. Next, the hybrid interphase model combined with FE-analysis was applied in order to evaluate the interphasial fiber-matrix stress field. According to this model the interphase thickness is not constant but it is property dependent. It was found that the stress field developed in the interphasial area is very sensitive to the mechanical properties of the nanotubes and the radial distance from the fiber. In addition, the stress field is sensitive to the fiber tip shape as investigated and confirmed in a previous publication by the authors [12].

REFERENCES

- [1] Papanicolaou, G.C., Michalopoulou, M.V., Anifantis, N.K., *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 62 (14), (2002), 1881-1894.
- [2] Rykov, V.T, Lukyanovich, V.M., Radushkevich, L.V, *Bulletin of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR Divisions of Chemical Science*, Vol. 1, Issue 3, (1952), 395-397.
- [3] Iijima, S., *Nature*, Vol. 354, (1991), 56-58.
- [4] Giannopoulos, G.I., Kakavas, P.A., Anifantis, N.K., *Computational Material Science*, Vol. 41, (2008), 561-569.
- [5] Yakobson, B., Smalley, R., *American Scientist*, Vol.85, (1997), Review of Nanotubes
- [6] Salvétat-Delmotte, J.-P., Rubio, A., *Carbon*, Vol. 40, 1729-1734
- [7] Yu, M.-F., Files, B. S., Arepalli, S., Ruoff, R., *Physical Review Letters*, Vol. 84 (24), (2000), 5552-5555
- [8] Yu, M.-F., Lourie, O., Dyer, M.J, Maloni, Kelly, T. F., Ruoff, R. S., *Science*, Vol. 287 (28), (2000), 637-640.
- [9] Yakobson, B.I., Campbell, M.P., Brabec, C. J., Bernholc, J., *Computational Material Science*, Vol.8, (1997, 341-348).
- [10] Wang, Z. L., Gao, R. P., Poncharal, P., de Heer, W. A., Dai, Z. R., Pan, Z. W., *Material Science of Engineering C*, Vol. 16, (2001), 3-10.
- [11] Fisher, F. T., Bradshaw, R. D., Brinson, L. C., *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 63 (11), (2003), 1689-1703.
- [12] Papanicolaou, G.C., Anifantis, N.K., Keppas, L.K., Kosmidou, Th.V., *Composite Interfaces*, Vol. 14, N.2, (2007), 131-152(22).
- [13] Pompe, G., Mäder, E., *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 60, (2000), 2159-2167.

- [14] Jayaraman, K., Reifsnider, K. L., Swain, R.E., Journal of Composite Technology and Research, Vol. 15, (1993), 14-22.
- [15] Chouchaoui, C. S., Benzeggah, M. L., Composites Science and Technology, Vol. 57, (1997), 617-622.
- [16] Lipatov, Yu. S., International Polymer and Technology Monograph, Vol. 2, (1977)
- [17] Wei Wu, K.Sadeghipour, K. Boberick, G.Baran, Materials Science and Engineering, A332, (2002), 362-372.
- [18] Seidel, G. D., Hammerand, D. C., Lagoudas, D. C., Sandia Report (2007).
- [19] Papanicolaou, G. C., Bakos, D. J., Kosmidou, Th. V., Composites, part A Vol. 38, (2007), 1099-1106.

Figure 1. (a) Flexural Modulus variation for different fiber loadings, (b) Relative flexural modulus relative variation for different fiber loadings.

Figure 2. (a) Flexural Strength variation for different fiber loadings, (b) Relative flexural strength variation for different fiber loadings.

Figure 3. (a) Failure Strain variation for different fiber loadings, (b) Relative failure strain for different fiber loadings.

Figure 4. RVE along with the hybrid interphase concept

Figure 5. Elastic material property variation within the hybrid interphase area for different degrees of adhesion.

Figure 6. (a) Typical finite element model corresponding to a flat fiber tip, (b) magnified area for better resolution of the mesh on the boundaries

Table 1 Interphase thickness for various adhesion coefficients

k	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.99
t_E (nm)	586.19	233.53	105.4	41.19	1.7
t_v (nm)	291.45	107.72	46.58	17.02	0.67

Table 2 Size of axisymmetric finite element model in the analysis

Linear Elements	Nodes	Fiber Radius	Fiber Length	RVE Radius	RVE Length
10891	10779	13 nm	200 nm	316 nm	400 nm

Table 3 Epoxy resin's and carbon nanotubes' mechanical properties of elasticity according to ref.[18],(All moduli, in GPa)

E_{matrix}	ν_{matrix}	E_{f11}	E_{f22}	E_{f12}	E_{f23}	ν_{f12}	ν_{f23}
3.08	0.3	704	345.54	227.04	125.52	0.14	0.3764